

EFFECT OF PLYOMETRIC AGILITY DRILL TRAINING ON AGILITY AMONG HOCKEY PLAYERS

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Abstract

The current research set out to examine how hockey players' agility improved after participating in plyometric agility drills. Thirty male hockey players from an associated college at Bharathidasan University in Tamil Nadu, India, were chosen in 2021 to fulfil the study's objectives. The age range of the subjects is 18–25 years. There were a total of 30 participants, 15 in the experimental group and 15 in the control group. The experimental group spent six weeks training using plyometric agility drills. Throughout the research, the control group did not get any kind of instruction. The research used agility as its criteria variable. The Illinois Agility Test (IAT) was used to assess the individuals' agility. Both the pre- and post-training assessments were administered at the beginning and end of the six-week training sessions, respectively. The means of the pre- and post-test data for the experimental and control groups were analysed using the statistical approach of the 't' ratio. On the criteria variable, the findings showed that there was a substantial difference. The reason for the difference is that the experimental group received plyometric agility drill training for agility, whereas the control group did not.

Keywords: Training in plyometric agility drills, agility, and the "t" ratio.

INTRODUCTION

Jumping, hopping, bounding, and skipping are the foundational motions of plyometric training, an exercise technique. The performance is lightning quick and full of tremendous energy (Lloyd, 2012). When compared to other power-based training methods, this one is rather unique. Your bodyweight is the only external force as you rapidly and repeatedly touch the ground. Muscle tissue acts as a force absorber during the eccentric phase and then acts as an actuator during the concentric phase, releasing the force it has absorbed. Your body is transforming this energy into something you can use throughout the changeover period. Research has shown that plyometric exercise may increase running-based endurance performance by increasing your running economy. Therefore, it is recommended that endurance athletes include plyometric training into their training regimens (Spurrs, 2005). Athletes who participate in team sports must possess agility, among other key qualities. The capacity to swiftly and efficiently alter one's body's posture and direction of movement is one definition. All the while keeping sufficient neuromuscular control. Agility also requires quickness of reaction, excellent balance, speed, and coordination. The mental capacity to adapt to novel circumstances is essential.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Selection of subjects

Researching how hockey players' agility improved after participating in plyometric agility drills was the primary goal of the research. College hockey players, both male and female, were randomly chosen to participate in the research. People ranging in age from 18 to 25 made up the sample.

Selection of variable

Independent variable

- Plyometric agility drill training

Dependent variable

- Agility

EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

A plyometric agility drill training group (the Experimental Group) and a control group, each consisting of fifteen individuals, were formed from the pool of participants. For six weeks, the experimental group trained with plyometric agility drills five days a week. The control group consisted of students who did not participate in any additional physical education classes beyond what was required by their course of study. The criteria variable used for this study was agility, a measure of motor fitness. Every single participant in both groups was evaluated using a predetermined set of criteria. Both before and after the training course, participants took the Illinois Agility Test (IAT) to gauge their level of agility.

Statistical technique

The ‘t’ test was used to analysis the significant differences, if any, difference between the groups respectively.

Level of significance

The 0.05 level of confidence was fixed to test the level of significance which was considered as an appropriate.

ANALYSIS OF THE DATA

The significance of the difference among the means of the experimental group was found out by pre-test. The data were analysed and dependent ‘t’ test was used with 0.05 levels as confidence.

TABLE I
Analysis of t-ratio for the pre and post tests of experimental and control group on
Agility
 (Scores in seconds)

Variables	Group	Standard Deviation		Sd Error	
		Pre	Post	Pre	Post
Agility	Control Group	0.76	0.74	0.197	0.192
	Experimental Group	0.69	0.70	0.180	0.182

TABLE II

Variables	Group	Mean		Degree of freedom	't' ratio
		Pre	Post		
Agility	Control Group	16.93	16.92	14	0.32
	Experimental Group	16.86	16.55	14	18.96*

**Significance at .05 level of confidence.*

The Table-I and II shows that the mean values of pre-test and post-test of the control group on agility were 16.93 and 16.92 respectively. The obtained 't' ratio was 0.32, since the obtained 't' ratio was less than the required table value of 2.14 for the significant at 0.05 level with 14 degrees of freedom it was found to be statistically insignificant. The mean values of pre- test and post-test of the experimental group on agility were 16.86 and 16.55 respectively. The obtained 't' ratio was 18.96* since the obtained 't' ratio was greater than the required table value of 2.14 for significance at 0.05 level with 14 degrees of freedom it was found to be statistically significant. The result of the study showed that there was a significant difference between control group and experimental group in agility. It may be concluded from the result of the study that experimental group improved in agility due to six weeks of plyometric agility drill training.

Figure-1
Bar Diagram Showing the Pre and Post Mean Values of
Experimental and Control Group on Agility

DISCUSSIONS ON FINDINGS

The study's results show that, in comparison to the control group, the experimental group—those who participated in plyometric agility drill training—had a significant improvement in the dependent variable—in this case, agility. Additionally, compared to the control group, plyometric agility drill training produces significant improvements.

CONCLUSION

After the training period, the experimental group demonstrated much higher agility than the control group, according to the data. A significant improvement in agility was seen. Nevertheless, after six weeks of training in plyometric agility drills, the experimental group showed more progress.

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